

**Beyond Science and Decisions:
From Problem Formulation to Dose-Response.
Report from Workshop III**

Appendices

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Appendix A. Meeting Participants

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Appendix B. Meeting Agenda

Workshop III Agenda

Date: May 4 – 6, 2011

Location: Noblis, Falls Church, VA

Purpose: To advance the recommendations in the NRC (2009) report concerning issue identification (problem formulation) and dose-response analysis through review of illustrative case studies for further development of a methods text

Day 1: Wednesday, May 4

Welcome, Introduction and Opening Remarks (8:15 a.m. to 8:45 a.m.)

- **Dr. David Evans**, Noblis
- Members of the Dose-Response Assessment Advisory Committee:
 - **Julie Fitzpatrick**, Environmental Protection Agency
 - **Roberta Grant**, Texas Commission on Environmental Quality
 - **Lynn Pottenger**, The Dow Chemical Company

Keynote Talk (8:45 a.m. to 9:30 a.m.)

- **Rita Schoeny**, U.S. Environmental Protection Agency. Experience at EPA in Problem Formulation Relevant to Both Ecological and Human Dose-Response Analysis.

Morning Break (9:30 a.m. to 10:00 a.m.)

Science Panel Discussion of Questions Related to Problem Formulation (10:00 a.m. to 11:15 a.m.)

Presentation of Framework (11:15 a.m. to noon)¹

¹ Including the integration of accepted case studies:

Biologically-informed empirical dose response: using linked cause-effect functions (TiO₂) (**Haber**)

Use of categorical regression to calculate risk above the RfD (copper, chemical T) (**Danziesen, Haber**)

Use of human data in cancer risk assessment (1,3-butadiene) (**Albertini, Sielken**)

Quantitative human health assessment based on ovarian effects in rodents (1,3-butadiene) (**Kirman, Grant**)

AEGL methodology (ethylbenzene) (**Camacho**)

Tiered screening approach for acute inhalation exposures (pentene) (**Grant**)

Consideration of human kinetic variability (trichloroethylene) (**Lipscomb**)

Multiple modes of action and risk assessment modeling (acrylamide) (**Hertzberg**)

Application of silver book methodology (dioxin) (**Simon**)

Estimate risk above the RfD using uncertainty factor distributions (multiple) (**Spalt**)

Use of biomarkers with the BMD method (methyl mercury) (**Gentry**)

Sustainable Futures Screening (isodecyl acrylate) (**E. Becker**)

Evaluating biological plausibility of linear low-dose extrapolation for risk of morbidity and mortality from hepatic disease (ethanol) (**R. Becker**)

- **Lynne Haber**, Toxicology Excellence for Risk Assessment

Lunch Speaker (Noon to 1:00 p.m.)

- **Bette Meek**, University of Ottawa. Increasing Assessment and Management Efficiency – the Importance of “Fit for Purpose” MOA/Human Relevance Analysis

Science Panel Discussion of Questions Related to Mode of Action (1:00 p.m. to 2:30 p.m.)

Observer Comments (2:30 p.m. to 3:00 p.m.)

Afternoon Break (3:00 p.m. to 3:30 p.m.)

Review of New Case Studies (3:30 p.m. to 5:30 p.m.)

- Risk-risk tradeoff (N-propyl bromide vs. perchloroethylene) (**Clewell, Finkel**)
- Children’s risk and use of epidemiology data? (lead) (**Carrington**)
- Comparison of the Hattis strawman approach and BMDs/UFs for noncancer endpoints (carbonyl sulfide and tetrachlorobenzene) (**Hattis**)

Dinner (on your own)

Day 2: Thursday, May 5

Review of New Case Studies Continued (8:00 a.m. to 9:30 a.m.)

- Quantitative assessment of sensitivity and variability in humans (chlorpyrifos and PON1) (**Price**)
- Biomonitoring equivalents (trihalomethanes) (**Aylward**)
- Endogenous/Background DNA Damage (vinyl chloride) (**Pottenger**)

Keynote Talk (9:30 a.m. to 10:00 a.m.)

- **Resha Putzrath**, U.S Navy. Incompatible Models? Low-Dose Linearity for Noncancer Risks and Dose Additivity for Mixtures

Morning Break (10:00 a.m. to 10:30 a.m.)

Report on Case Study Progress from Workshop II (10:30 a.m. to noon)

- BBDR for respiratory tract carcinogenicity (formaldehyde) (**Clewell, Conolly**)
- Low-dose dose-response curve shape for genotoxic chemicals (multiple) (**Pottenger**)
- Implication of linear extrapolation to origin (multiple) (**Kroner**)
- Alternative temporal exposure patterns (generic and benzene) (**Haber**)
- Data fusion methods (petroleum hydrocarbons) (**Mohapatra**)

Lunch Speaker (Noon to 1:00 p.m.)

- **James Swenberg**, University of North Carolina. Endogenous and Background DNA Adducts as a Means of Understanding Mode of Action (MOA) in the Low End of the Dose Response Curve

Science Panel Discussion of Questions Related to Background and Endogenous Exposure and Background Response (1:00 p.m. to 3:00 p.m.)

Afternoon Break (3:00 p.m. to 3:30 p.m.)

Observer Comments (3:30 p.m. to 4:00 p.m.)

Science Panel Discussion of Additional Cross-Cutting NAS Issues (4:00 p.m. to 5:30 p.m.)

Dinner (on your own)

Day 3: Friday, May 6

Science Panel Discussion (8:30 a.m. to 10:00 a.m.)

- Consideration of areas where methods/cases are missing
- Publication structure and writing assignments

Morning Break (10:00 a.m. to 10:30 a.m.)

Observer Comments/Open Discussion (10:30 a.m. to 11:30 a.m.)

Closing Remarks (11:30 a.m. to noon)

Adjournment

Appendix C. Expert Panel Biographies

Michael Bolger, U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA)

Michael Bolger received his Bachelor's degree in Biology in 1971 from Villanova University and his doctoral degree in Physiology and Biophysics in 1976 from Georgetown University. After a 3-year postdoctoral position at the Georgetown University Medical Center, Dr. Bolger became a staff fellow in toxicology with the Bureau of Foods in the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA). Upon completion of his staff fellowship, he accepted a position as a toxicologist with the Contaminants Branch at the FDA. Since 1980, Dr. Bolger has been involved in the hazard/safety/risk assessment of anthropogenic and naturally derived contaminants in food. Dr. Bolger is a board-certified toxicologist by the American Board of Toxicology. Dr. Bolger is the recipient of the 2009 Arnold J. Lehman Award conferred by the Society of Toxicology and the 2010 Outstanding Risk Practitioner Award conferred by the Society of Risk Analysis. Dr. Bolger is currently Director of the Chemical Hazards Assessment Staff in the Office of Food Safety, which is responsible for the hazard/safety/risk assessment of food-borne contaminants and for reporting FDA monitoring efforts on food-borne environmental contaminants as well as the conduct of exposure assessments. Dr. Bolger is currently serving as a food safety expert of the World Health Organization and as a member of the Joint Expert Committee on Food Additives and the Foodborne Disease Burden Epidemiology Reference Group of the World Health Organization.

James S. Bus, The Dow Chemical Company

James S. Bus is the Director of External Technology, Toxicology and Environmental Research and Consulting at The Dow Chemical Company (1989–present). He previously held positions as Associate Director of Toxicology and Director of Drug Metabolism at The Upjohn Company (1986–1989), Senior Scientist at the Chemical Industry Institute of Toxicology (CIIT, 1977–1986), and Assistant Professor of Toxicology, University of Cincinnati (1975–1977). Dr. Bus currently participates in several external institutions, including the Board of Directors of The Hamner Institutes (formerly CIIT) and the National Academy of Sciences/National Research Council Board on Environmental Studies and Toxicology (BEST). He has also served as Chair of the American Chemistry Council and International Council of Chemical Associations Long-Range Research Initiatives; the EPA Chartered Science Advisory Board (2003–2009); and the FDA National Center for Toxicological Research Science Advisory Board (2004–2010). He serves as an Associate Editor of *Toxicology and Applied Pharmacology* and on the Editorial Boards of *Environmental Health Perspectives* and *Dose Response*. Dr. Bus is a member of the Society of Toxicology (serving as President in 1996–97), the American Society for Pharmacology and Experimental Therapeutics, the American Conference of Governmental and Industrial Hygienists, and the Teratology Society. He is a Diplomate and Past-President of the American Board of Toxicology and a Fellow of the Academy of Toxicological Sciences (member of Board of Directors, 2008–present; Vice-President and President-Elect, 2010). Dr. Bus received the Society of Toxicology Achievement Award (1987) for outstanding contributions to the science of toxicology, the Society of Toxicology Founders Award (2010) for leadership fostering the role of toxicology in improving safety decisions, Rutgers University

Robert A. Scala Award (1999) for exceptional work as a toxicologist in an industry laboratory, and the K.E. Moore Outstanding Alumnus Award (Michigan State University, Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology). He received his B.S. in Medicinal Chemistry from the University of Michigan (1971) and Ph.D. in Pharmacology from Michigan State University (1975) and currently is an Adjunct Professor in the Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology at that institution. His research interests include mechanisms of oxidant toxicity, defense mechanisms to chemical toxicity, relationship of pharmacokinetics to expression of chemical toxicity, and general pesticide and industrial chemical toxicology. He has authored/co-authored more than 100 publications, books and scientific reviews.

John Christopher, CH2M/Hill

John Christopher recently joined CH2M/Hill as a toxicologist. Prior to joining CH2MHill, he was a staff toxicologist with the Department of Toxic Substances Control, California Environmental Protection Agency. In this position he reviews, critiques, and approves assessments of risk to human health and ecological risk assessments at military facilities and other hazardous waste sites and permitted facilities in California. He constructs multi-pathway risk assessments to identify numerical criteria for classifying hazardous levels of metals and organic chemicals in waste. He also uses Monte Carlo methods in various exposure settings to identify levels protective of human health. He has received Certificates of Recognition for contributions resulting in the successful transfer of a hazardous waste landfill at a former naval shipyard in Vallejo, CA; for a prescribed burn to uncover unexploded ordnance at a former fort in, Monterey, CA; and for cleanup of a fleet industrial supply center in Alameda, CA. In addition, he has received a Sustained Superior Accomplishment Award from the California Department of Toxic Substances Control for risk assessment of metals in hazardous waste. Prior to his current position with the State of California, Dr. Christopher conducted risk assessments for ICF Kaiser Engineers and IT Corporation. He also worked for research laboratories, where he conducted and managed animal studies. Dr. Christopher earned a B.S. in Biology from Georgetown University, Washington, DC and a M.A. in Pharmacology from Stanford University, Palo Alto, CA. He received his Ph.D. in Biological Science from Oregon State University, Corvallis, OR. Dr. Christopher is a Diplomate of the American Board of Toxicology and a former member of this Board. He has served as President and held several other offices in the Risk Assessment Specialty Section of the Society of Toxicology and also in SOT's Northern California Chapter. He is a peer reviewer for *Toxicological Sciences*, *Risk Analysis*, *Human and Ecological Risk Assessment*, and *CRC Critical Reviews in Toxicology*.

Rory Conolly, EPA National Health and Environmental Effects Research Laboratory

Rory Conolly is a Senior Research Biologist in the Integrated Systems Toxicology Division of EPA's National Health and Environmental Effects Research Laboratory in Research Triangle Park, North Carolina, USA. His major research interests are: (1) biological mechanisms of dose-response and time-course behaviors, (2) the use of computational modeling to study these mechanisms, and (3) the application of computational models to quantitative dose-response assessment. Dr. Conolly received the U.S. Society of Toxicology's (SOT) Lehman Award for lifetime achievement in risk assessment in 2005. He was a member of the National Academy of

Sciences Board on Environmental Studies and Toxicology from 2004 until joining EPA in 2005, President of the SOT Biological Modeling Specialty Section (2000–2001), President of the SOT Risk Assessment Specialty Section (1997–1998), and a member of the SOT Risk Assessment Task Force (1998–2000) as well as currently serving as a Councilor with the Risk Assessment Specialty Section. He is an Adjunct Professor of Biomathematics at North Carolina State University; Faculty Affiliate, Department of Environmental and Radiological Health Sciences, Colorado State University; and has four times received awards from the SOT Risk Assessment Specialty Section (1991, 1999, 2003, and 2004). Dr. Conolly was born in London, England, and raised in Canada and the United States. He received a Bachelor's degree in Biology from Harvard College in 1972, a doctorate in Physiology/Toxicology from the Harvard School of Public Health in 1978, and spent a postdoctoral year at the Central Toxicology Laboratory of Imperial Chemical Industries, PLC, in Cheshire, England. He was a member of the Toxicology Faculty at The University of Michigan School of Public Health from 1979 through 1986, and worked with the U.S. Air Force Toxic Hazards Research Division, Wright-Patterson Air Force Base, in Ohio from 1986 until 1989. In 1989, Dr. Conolly joined the Chemical Industry Institute of Toxicology (CIIT) and worked there until 2005, when he joined EPA.

Mike Dourson, Toxicology Excellence for Risk Assessment (TERA)

Mike Dourson is the President of Toxicology Excellence for Risk Assessment (TERA). He has a Ph.D. in Toxicology from the University of Cincinnati in 1980 and is a Diplomate of the American Board of Toxicology (ABT). He has led TERA's development of partnerships among diverse groups to address chemicals of high visibility, such as formaldehyde and perchlorate, and cooperative ventures such as the Alliance for Risk Assessment. He also worked for 15 years at EPA, holding leadership roles and winning awards for joint efforts, such as the creation of EPA's IRIS. In 2003, he won the Society of Toxicology (SOT) Lehman award. In 2007, he was elected a Fellow of the Academy of Toxicological Sciences. In 2009, he won the International Society of Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology's International Achievement. In 2009, he was also selected a Fellow for the Society for Risk Analysis (SRA). Dr. Dourson has co-published more than 100 papers on risk methods or assessments for specific chemicals. He has also co-authored well over 100 government risk assessment documents, made more than 100 invited presentations, and chaired more than 100 sessions at scientific meetings and independent peer reviews. He has been elected to multiple officer positions in the ABT, SOT and SRA. In addition to numerous appointments on government panels, including chairing roles, he is also a media resource specialist in risk assessment for the SOT, member on the editorial board of several journals, and vice-chair of the NSF International Health Advisory Board.

Adam M. Finkel, UMDNJ School of Public Health

Adam M. Finkel is one of the Nation's leading experts in the evolving field of quantitative risk assessment and cost-benefit analysis, with 25 years of experience improving methods of analysis and making risk-based decisions to protect workers and the general public from environmental hazards. Dr. Finkel is currently a Fellow at the Penn Law School and Executive Director of the Penn Program on Regulation; he is also a Professor of Environmental and Occupational Health at the University of Medicine and Dentistry of New Jersey (UMDNJ) School of Public Health. From 2004 to 2008, he was a Visiting Professor of Public and International Affairs at the

Woodrow Wilson School at Princeton University. From 1995 to 2003, he was Director of Health Standards Programs at the U.S. Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) and was responsible for promulgating and evaluating regulations to protect the Nation's workers from chemical, radiological and biological hazards; he then served as OSHA's Regional Administrator for the Rocky Mountain States. He recently received the David P. Rall Award from the American Public Health Association for "a career in advancing science in the service of public health protection." Dr. Finkel has a Sc.D. in Environmental Health Sciences from the Harvard School of Public Health, a Master's degree in Public Policy from Harvard's John F. Kennedy School of Government, and an A.B. in Biology from Harvard College; he is a Certified Industrial Hygienist.

R. Jeffrey Lewis, ExxonMobil Biomedical Sciences, Inc.

R. Jeffrey Lewis is a Senior Scientific Associate with ExxonMobil Biomedical Sciences, Inc. In this position Dr. Lewis is responsible for providing support to ExxonMobil's epidemiology and health risk assessment scientific programs. He currently manages company scientific programs related to children's health, emerging environmental health issues, legislative/regulatory affairs, and regulatory impact analysis (e.g., benefit-cost analysis). He has served on a number of industry trade association scientific committees and external science advisory boards (e.g., Peer Consultation panel for EPA's Voluntary Children's Chemical Evaluation Program) and is a member of ExxonMobil's Occupational Exposure Limits Committee. Dr. Lewis also has an adjunct faculty appointment at the University of Texas School of Public Health and is currently Treasurer Elect of the Society for Risk Analysis. Dr. Lewis received his B.S. degree in Biology from the University of Kansas in 1985 and an M.S. and Ph.D. in Epidemiology from the University of Texas School of Public Health in 1987 and 1990, respectively. In addition, he earned an M.B.A. from Rutgers University in 1997.

Randall O. Manning, Georgia Department of Natural Resources, Environmental Protection Division

Randall Manning has served as the Environmental Toxicology Coordinator for the Georgia Department of Natural Resources, Environmental Protection Division (EPD), since 1990. In that role, Dr. Manning has worked with all of the media programs in EPD to encourage the use and consistency of current risk assessment approaches. Dr. Manning worked extensively with the development of risk-based evaluations for the State Hazardous Site Response Act (state superfund program). He has also worked with water quality programs, both related to water quality standards and fish tissue risk assessment approaches and advisories. In addition, Dr. Manning has worked with the statewide air monitoring program in developing a monitoring network and guidelines for evaluations of air toxics. Dr. Manning received B.S., M.S. and Ph.D. degrees from the University of Georgia. He is a Diplomate of the American Board of Toxicology.

Bette Meek, McLaughlin Centre for Population Health Risk Assessment, University of Ottawa

Bette Meek has a background in toxicology receiving her M.Sc. in Toxicology (with distinction) from the University of Surrey, United Kingdom, and her Ph.D. in Risk Assessment from the University of Utrecht, The Netherlands. She is currently the Associate Director of Chemical Risk Assessment at the McLaughlin Centre for Population Health Risk Assessment, University of Ottawa, completing an interchange assignment from Health Canada. She has extensive experience in the management of chemical assessment programs within the Government of Canada, most recently involving development and implementation of process and methodology for the health assessment of Existing Substances under the Canadian Environmental Protection Act (CEPA) and, previously, in programs for contaminants in drinking water and air.

With colleagues within Canada and internationally, she has contributed to or led initiatives to increase transparency, defensibility and efficiency in health risk assessment, having convened and participated in initiatives in this area for numerous organizations, including the International Programme on Chemical Safety, the World Health Organization, the International Life Sciences Institute, the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, the U.S. National Academy of Sciences, and the U.S. National Institute for Environmental Health Sciences. Relevant areas have included frameworks for weight of evidence analysis, including mode of action, chemical-specific adjustment factors, physiologically based pharmacokinetic modeling, combined exposures, and predictive modeling. She has also authored more than 175 publications in the area of chemical risk assessment and received several awards for contribution in this domain.

Greg Paoli, Risk Sciences International

Greg Paoli serves as Principal Risk Scientist and COO at Risk Sciences International, a consulting firm specializing in risk assessment, management and communication in the field of public health, safety and risk-based decision-support. Mr. Paoli has experience in diverse risk domains, including toxicological, microbiological and nutritional hazards; air and water quality; climate change impacts; medical and engineering devices; and emergency planning and response for natural and man-made disasters. He specializes in probabilistic risk assessment methods, the development of risk-based decision-support tools, and comparative risk assessment. Mr. Paoli has served on a number of expert committees devoted to the risk sciences. He was a member of the U.S. National Research Council (U.S. NRC) committee that issued the 2009 report *Science and Decisions: Advancing Risk Assessment*. He serves on the Canadian Standards Association Technical Committee on Risk Management, advisory committees of the National Roundtable on the Environment and the Economy, and a U.S. NRC Standing Committee on the Use of Public Health Data at the U.S. Food Safety and Inspection Service, and he has served on several expert committees convened by the World Health Organization. Mr. Paoli completed a term as Councilor of the Society for Risk Analysis (SRA) and is a member of the Editorial Board of *Risk Analysis*. Recently, Mr. Paoli was awarded the Sigma Xi-SRA Distinguished Lecturer Award. He has provided training in risk assessment methods around the world, including the continuing education programs of the Harvard School of Public Health and the University of Maryland. Mr. Paoli holds a Bachelors Degree in Electrical and Computer Engineering and a Master's Degree in Systems Design Engineering from the University of Waterloo.

Rita Schoeny, EPA Office of Water

Rita Schoeny is Senior Science Advisor for EPA's Office of Water. She received her B.S. in Biology at the University of Dayton and a Ph.D. in Microbiology from the School of Medicine of the University of Cincinnati. After completing a postdoctoral fellowship at the Kettering Laboratory, Department of Environmental Health, she was appointed Assistant Professor in that department of the U.C. Medical School. Dr. Schoeny has held several adjunct appointments and regularly lectures at colleges and universities on risk assessment. She has given lectures and courses on risk assessment in many areas of the world. Dr. Schoeny joined EPA in 1986. Prior to her current position, she was Associate Director of the Health and Ecological Criteria Division of the Office of Science and Technology, Office of Water. She has been responsible for major assessments and programs in support of the Safe Drinking Water Act, including scientific support for rules on disinfectant by-products, arsenic, microbial contaminants, and the first set of regulatory determinations from the Contaminant Candidate List. She has held various positions in the Office of Research and Development, including Chief of the Methods Evaluation and Development Staff, Environmental Criteria and Assessment Office, Cincinnati; Associate Director NCEA-Cincinnati; and chair of the Agency-wide workgroup to review cancer risk assessments. Dr. Schoeny has published in the areas of metabolism and mutagenicity of PCBs and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, assessment of complex environmental mixtures, health and ecological effects of mercury, drinking water contaminants, and principles and practice of human health risk assessment. She was a lead and co-author of the *Mercury Study Report to Congress* and was a principal scientist and manager for the Ambient Water Quality Criterion for Methylmercury. She has been the chair of an EPA working group on the use of genetic toxicity data in determining mode of action for carcinogens. She participates in many EPA scientific councils as well as national and international scientific advisory and review groups. Current involvement includes panels on the interpretation of DNA adduct data for risk assessment and evaluation of episodic and less-than-lifetime exposure to carcinogens. Dr. Schoeny is the recipient of several awards, including several EPA Gold, Silver and Bronze Medals; EPA's Science Achievement Award for Health Sciences; the Greater Cincinnati Area Federal Employee of the Year Award; the University of Cincinnati Distinguished Alumnae Award; Staff Choice Award for Management Excellence; and the FDA Teamwork Award for publication of national advice on mercury-contaminated fish.